

**The Impact of COVID-19 on the Police Personnel Working
in Cyberabad**

(Policy Paper 07)

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Appendix C

Questionnaire used for research study

Basic Information

1. Email
2. Name of the Officer
3. Age
4. Gender
5. Rank
6. Area/Police Station
7. Type of Duty (Select one):
 - Law and Order (Bandobast)
 - Law and Order (Patrolling)
 - Law and Order (Reception)
 - Law and Order (Other Desk Job)
 - Traffic
 - Armed Reserve
 - Crime & Investigation

Health Details

1. Weight (Before COVID)
2. Weight (After COVID)
3. Height
4. Co-morbidities (Tick all that apply):
 - Hypertension
 - Alcohol
 - Smoking
 - Heart Disease
 - Diabetes
 - Kidney Disease
 - Liver Disease
 - Cancer
 - None

Fitness & Lifestyle

1. Exercise Level (Select one):
 - No regular exercise
 - Mild (<30 min/day)
 - Moderate (30–60 min/day)
 - Strenuous (>1 hour/day)
2. Type of Exercise (Select one):
 - Yoga

- Pranayama
 - Aerobic exercise (walking, jogging, running, cycling, swimming)
 - Weight training
3. Type of Food (Select one): Veg / Non-Veg
 4. Able to Have Meals on Time (Select one): Yes / No
 5. Working Hours (Select one):
 - 8 hours
 - 8–12 hours
 - 12–16 hours
 6. Work Timings (Select one):
 - Day duty
 - Night duty
 - Mostly day duty
 - Mostly night duty
 7. Sleep Pattern (Select one): Normal / Lack of sleep
 8. No. of Sleep Hours (Select one):
 - 4–6 hours
 - 6–8 hours

Vaccination Details

1. COVID Vaccination Type (Select one):
 - Covaxin
 - Covishield
 - Sputnik V
2. COVID Vaccination Doses Taken:
 - None
 - One
 - Two
 - Booster
3. COVID Vaccination First Dose (Date)
4. COVID Vaccination Second Dose (Date)
5. COVID Vaccination Third Dose (Date)

COVID Infection Details

1. COVID Infection Status (Select one): Infected / Not infected
2. Place of Acquiring Infection (Select one): Work / Home
3. Type of Positive Test: Rapid Antigen Test / RTPCR
4. Infected during (Tick all that apply):
 - First wave
 - Second wave
 - Third wave
5. Date of Infection
6. Days of Leave Availed
7. Hospitalisation (Select one): Yes / No

8. Days of Hospitalisation
9. Total Days Until Recovery (Select one):
 - Less than 7 days
 - 7-15 days
 - More than 15 days
10. Oxygen Requirement (Select one): Yes / No
11. Ventilator Need (Select one): Yes / No
12. Recovered (Select one): Yes / No
13. Persisting Symptoms After One Month (Select one): Yes / No
14. Symptoms Experienced:
 - Breathing difficulty
 - Chest pain
 - Palpitation
 - Brain fog
 - Lack of sleep
 - Fatigue
15. New Onset Conditions Following COVID (Tick all that apply):
 - Diabetes
 - Hypertension
 - Fungal infections
16. Reduced Work Capability After COVID (Select one): Yes / No